

CONRAD-LIMPACH QUINOLINE SYNTHESIS WITH VARIOUS
ARYLAMINES AND ETHYL BENZOYLACETOACETATE.
PART I

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Aniline has been condensed with ethyl benzoylacetate in presence of a trace of hydrochloric acid as a catalyst, and the resulting anil, when directly cyclised in boiling diphenyl ether, afforded in good yields 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline, obtained by Desai and Shah (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 121) along with 4-hydroxy-2-methyl-3-benzoylquinoline, also obtained by the Friedel-Crafts benzoylation of 4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline. *Ortho*- and *para*-toluidines on similar condensations furnished 4-hydroxy-2:8-dimethyl-3-benzoylquinoline and 4-hydroxy-2:6-dimethyl-3-benzoylquinoline respectively, the condensation taking place solely with the acetyl group. β -Naphthylamine, however, yielded 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-5:6-benzoquinoline, obtained by the method of Desai and Shah (*loc. cit.*), the reaction occurring with the benzoyl group. *m*-Toluidine and methyl anthranilate did not give any solid product.

The synthesis of 4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline derivatives by the condensation of aniline and ethyl acetoacetate and subsequent cyclisation of ethyl acetoacetate-anil formed, and known after Conrad and Limpach (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 947), has been extensively investigated and various 4-hydroxy-2-methylquinolines have been synthesised. The studies have also included the effect of various catalysts like hydrochloric acid, piperidine, dimethylamine, etc., towards the formation of anil (Coffey, Thomson and Wilson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 858) and search for a suitable solvent for cyclisation. The solvents recommended for the purpose are paraffin or inert oil, diphenyl ether, diphenyl, Dowtherm 'A', etc.

The extension of the method towards the synthesis of 4-hydroxy-2-phenylquinoline by replacing ethyl acetoacetate by ethyl benzoylacetate has not been found as successful, though aniline and *m*-chloroaniline have been condensed with ethyl benzoylacetate and the corresponding quinoline derivatives have been obtained (Conrad and Limpach, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 521; Elderfield *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1272). However, no condensation has been carried out with *C*-acyl β -keto esters.

In connection with the work on the synthesis of 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline, obtained on cyclisation of the condensation product of benzauilide imidochloride with ethyl sodioacetoacetate (Desai and Shah, this *Journal* 1949, 26, 121) attempts were made to achieve another synthesis of the same which would further support the structure assigned to it. As attempts to get it by the Friedel-Crafts acetylation of 4-hydroxy-2-phenylquinoline met with failures, it was thought of interest to explore the Conrad-Limpach synthesis with aniline and ethyl benzoylacetate. Preliminary experiments in this direction showed that two products were obtained on cyclisation of the intermediate anil, and hence a systematic investigation was undertaken (Kulkarni, Thakor and Shah, *Curr. Sci.*, 1949, 18, 444).

As can be expected, aniline can eliminate a molecule of water with ethyl benzoylacetate in two ways, by reacting either with the carbonyl of the acetyl group or

of the benzoyl group, so as to afford either 4-hydroxy-2-methyl-3-benzoylquinoline (I) or 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline (II) on final cyclisation with the elimination of alcohol.

In the present case equimolecular quantities of aniline and ethyl benzoylacetate were condensed using a trace of hydrochloric acid as a catalyst and the resulting anil (an oil) suffered ring-closure with the elimination of alcohol in boiling diphenyl ether. The principal product isolated was found to be identical in all respects with the product obtained by Desai and Shah (*loc. cit.*) on cyclisation of the crude condensation product of benzanilide imidochloride with ethyl sodioacetate and has been assigned the structure 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline.

The mother-liquor after isolation of the above product, when examined, furnished yet another product (as shown by different properties and depression of m.p.) in small quantity, and it was found to be identical with the product obtained by the Friedel-Crafts benzoylation of 4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline, and evidently is 4-hydroxy-2-methyl-3-benzoylquinoline. The above reactions can be represented as:

It will be seen from above that the condensation takes place at both the centres as the corresponding quinoline derivatives have been obtained.

It is interesting to note that ethyl benzoylacetate with aniline gave a satisfactory yield (about 20%) of the final quinoline derivative, while the reaction of aniline with ethyl benzoylacetate gives poorer yields.

The reaction was extended to some other arylamines, like *o*-toluidine, *m*-toluidine, *p*-toluidine, β -naphthylamine, etc.

The reaction between *p*-toluidine and ethyl benzoylacetate yielded 4-hydroxy-2:6-dimethyl-3-benzoylquinoline as it differed considerably from the product obtained by Desai and Shah's method (*loc. cit.*) and agreed with the product obtained by the Friedel-Crafts benzoylation of 4-hydroxy-2:6-dimethylquinoline. The mixed m.p. of their oximes showed no depression.

The reaction between *o*-toluidine and ethyl benzoylacetate yielded similarly 4-hydroxy-2:8-dimethyl-3-benzoylquinoline, being the same as that obtained by the Friedel-Crafts benzoylation of 4-hydroxy-2:8-dimethylquinoline.

In these two cases the condensation took place solely with the acetyl group, as no other product could be isolated.

In the case of β -naphthylamine, however, the condensation took place at the benzoyl group and 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-5:6-benzoquinoline was formed, as its oxime did not depress the m.p. of the oxime of an authentic specimen prepared by the method of Desai and Shah (*loc. cit.*). *m*-Toluidine and methyl anthranilate on similar condensation did not yield any solid product.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of Aniline with Ethyl Benzoylacetate: 4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline and 4-Hydroxy-2-methyl-3-benzoylquinoline.—To a mixture of aniline (0.46 g.) and ethyl benzoylacetate (1.17 g.), a trace of hydrochloric acid was added by a glass rod and the mixture heated on a steam-bath for about an hour. It was then cooled and left overnight. Next day water was added and the ether extract taken up. The ether extract was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and then with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residual oil after evaporation of ether was poured in boiling diphenyl ether (10 c.c.) and the mixture heated for further half an hour, and left overnight. The substance separating was collected, washed with light petroleum and dried, m.p. 282-84°. Crystallisation from glacial acetic acid raised the m.p. to 289°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 4-hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetylquinoline obtained by the method of Desai and Shah (*loc. cit.*) was not depressed. Oxime, m.p. 262° and methyl ether, m.p. 218-19°, agreed with the specimens obtained by the method of Desai and Shah (*loc. cit.*).

The mother-liquor on dilution with petroleum gave a further precipitate, which on crystallisation from acetic acid gave more of the above product (total yield 0.25 g.).

The acetic acid mother-liquor on dilution with water gave a substance readily soluble in hot alcohol and thus different from the above. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 284° (yield 0.05 g.), and was found to be identical with 4-hydroxy-2-methyl-3-benzoylquinoline obtained by the Friedel-Crafts benzoylation of 4-hydroxy-2-methylquinoline, as described below.

Friedel-Crafts Reaction on 4-Hydroxy-2-methylquinoline with Benzoyl Chloride: 4-Hydroxy-2-methyl-3-benzoylquinoline.—4-Hydroxy-2-methylquinoline (1.6 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (3.0 g., 2 mols.) were thoroughly mixed and benzoyl chloride (1.2 c.c.) added. It was heated on an oil-bath at 155°-160° for one and half hours. It was cooled, ice and hydrochloric acid (3.0 c.c.) added and kept overnight. The next day the solid separating was collected, washed successively with water, sodium bicarbonate and boiling water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 282-83° (1.0 g.). (Found: N, 5.3. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 5.3 per cent). It is fairly soluble in alcohol, acetone and acetic acid, but it is almost insoluble in ether, petroleum, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride.

The *oxime* was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 252-54°. (Found: N, 10.0. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.1 per cent). 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. > 310°. (Found: N, 15.6. $C_{23}H_{17}O_4N_5$ requires N, 15.8 per cent).

Condensation of p-Toluidine with Ethyl Benzoylacetate: 4-Hydroxy-2:6-dimethyl-3-benzoylquinoline.—p-Toluidine (0.53 g.) and ethyl benzoylacetate (1.17 g.) were heated using a trace of hydrochloric acid and the product worked up as before. The cyclisation was carried out in boiling diphenyl ether (10 c.c.) and the product, isolated as before, was crystallised from alcohol in fine colorless needles, m.p. > 290° (0.2 g.). (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 5.1 per cent). The *oxime* was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 244°. (Found: N, 9.2. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.6 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-6-methylquinoline, obtained by Desai and Shah's method (*loc. cit.*) melts at 263° and is obviously different from the above.

Friedel-Crafts Reaction on 4-Hydroxy-2:6-dimethylquinoline with Benzoyl Chloride: 4-Hydroxy-2:6-dimethyl-3-benzoylquinoline.—4-Hydroxy-2:6-dimethylquinoline was prepared using a trace of hydrochloric acid as a catalyst. The separation of water was immediate. The cyclisation was carried out in diphenyl ether and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 276°.

The above quinoline (1.72 g., 1 mol.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.66 g., 2 mols.) were thoroughly mixed and benzoyl chloride (1.2 c.c., 1.1 mol.) added. It was heated at 150°-160° for 3 hours, cooled and ice and concentrated hydrochloric acid added and left overnight. The next day the solid was collected, washed with water, sodium bicarbonate and finally with boiling water. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. > 290° (0.5 g.). *Oxime*, m.p. and mixed m.p. 244°.

The mixture of this product and the one obtained from p-toluidine and ethyl benzoylacetate (above) did not melt up to 290°. The mixture of their oximes showed no depression in m.p..

Condensation of o-Toluidine with Ethyl Benzoylacetate: 4-Hydroxy-2:8-dimethyl-3-benzoylquinoline.—The amine (0.53 g.) and the ester (1.17 g.) were condensed as before and cyclisation carried out in boiling diphenyl ether (10 c.c.). The product obtained was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 289° (0.1 g.). (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 5.1 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-8-methylquinoline, obtained by Desai and Shah (*loc. cit.*), has m.p. 215°.

Friedel-Crafts Reaction on 4-Hydroxy-2:8-dimethylquinoline with Benzoyl Chloride: 4-Hydroxy-2:8-dimethyl-3-benzoylquinoline.—4-Hydroxy-2:8-dimethylquinoline (1 mol.), anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 mols.) and benzoyl chloride (1.1 mols.) were heated at 150°-160° for 3 hours and worked up as before. The product was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 289° (10%). Mixed m.p. with the above product was not lowered.

Condensation of β -Naphthylamine with Ethyl Benzoylacetate: 4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-5:6-benzoquinoline.—The amine (0.72 g.) and the ester (1.17 g.) were condensed as in the previous case and cyclisation carried out in diphenyl ether (10 c.c.). On addition of petroleum (b. p. 60°-80°) some pasty mass separated out which was collected and washed with petroleum (b. p. 60°-80°). It was then extracted with 10% sodium hydroxide and the extract acidified and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. > 300° (0.2 g.). (Found: N, 4.5. $C_{21}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 4.5 per cent). The oxime was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 260 (Found: N, 8.6. $C_{21}H_{15}O_2N_2$ requires N, 8.5 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-2-phenyl-3-acetyl-5:6-benzoquinoline, prepared by the method of Desai and Shah (*loc. cit.*), has m.p. > 300°; oxime, m.p. 260°. Mixed m.p. of the two oximes was not lowered.

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